

Farmer Clusters: Farmers achieve more together in the Mostviertel in the name of biodiversity

Policy recommendations

The Farmer Cluster in the Mostviertel region has demonstrated that a network of farmers can contribute very effectively to increasing biodiversity in grassland. What makes the collaboration in the Farmer Cluster so special is the direct exchange between farmers, where experiences can be shared and discussed on an equal footing. To promote Farmer Clusters as an effective approach to improve biodiversity, environmental outcomes, and sustainability across farm landscapes the following policies are recommended:

- **Invest in long-term facilitation and support.** Government and rural development policies should embed training, resourcing, and financing for Farmer Cluster facilitators as core elements of agri-environmental programmes. By supporting skilled facilitators to build trust, coordinate activity, and link farmers to external expertise, policies can enable Farmer Clusters to deliver long-term benefits for biodiversity and rural communities. For Austrian farmers it would, of course, be best if the facilitator also came from the agricultural sector and brought a great deal of practical knowledge. This would prevent the impression that there might be hierarchical differences.
- **Enhance access to advice, training, and monitoring tools.** Policy should prioritise funding for knowledge exchange platforms, tailored training, and shared monitoring protocols, ensuring farmers have the information, tools, and support needed to implement, assess, and adapt their conservation efforts within their clusters.
- **Maintain voluntary, group-based incentives within AES.** The Mostviertel Farmer Cluster has demonstrated the importance of creating voluntary incentives for practical implementation, so the focus should continue to be on voluntary measures. Raising farmers' awareness of the benefits of implementing measures for biodiversity is also important. Develop and embed flexible incentives that reward collaborative action and enable collective results within AES. Build on successful pilots across Europe to embed group result-based payments and voluntary clustering as core elements of national policy, reinforcing both rural resilience and ecological benefits.
- **Supporting awareness of biodiversity.** Informing the public and farmers can increase acceptance of biodiversity conservation measures. BioBlitzes for schoolchildren and adults could also help.

Transformative impact of Farmer Clusters on farmland biodiversity

Farmland biodiversity is in decline, threatening both agroecosystem services and long-term food system resilience. While agri-environmental schemes (AES) aim to reverse this trend, uptake and impact vary widely. Traditional top-down AES often fail to connect with farmers' local realities, values, and identity. In contrast, the Farmer Cluster approach offers a promising alternative. Farmer Clusters empower farmers to achieve their farming and environmental goals. By working together under the guidance of a skilled facilitator, farmers can tackle landscape-level restoration and have a greater impact than any one individual could accomplish alone. Using a "bottom-up" approach, farmers

identify their conservation priorities and choose which practices to implement collectively. This is an impactful way to address global issues such as biodiversity conservation at the landscape scale. As well as the conservation benefits, Farmer Clusters can create support networks in rural communities, bridging gaps between policy-makers and farmers, and fostering both regional and national cohesion.

Approach and results

The EU Horizon 2020 project FRAMEwork explores the potential to replicate the Farmer Cluster model across Europe to enhance farmland biodiversity at a continental scale. Between 2020 and 2021, eleven clusters, regrouping 124 farms, were established in eight countries: the UK, Austria, the Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Spain, and varied in size, farming system, organisational structure, and the degree of connectivity between farms. Biodiversity-friendly practices introduced by the Farmer Clusters include the introduction of wildflower margins, meadow restoration, hedgerow and tree planting, and the installation of bird boxes. Particularly in the Mostviertel, the farmers decided to resow species-rich oat grass meadows and wildflower margins. For the reseeding, different devices were used depending on the soil and grassland conditions. The slot seeder, for example, was used because the turf was not very dense. Before reseeding the meadow was cut to 5 cm in length. For other meadows pre-treatment was necessary. In another case due to a very dense turf, and a strong growth of the previous grassland vegetation, it had to be destroyed before the seeding. The first step was to use a cultivator, in the second step a reverse tiller, combined with a seeder, was applied to put the old turf upside down and to bring up the bare soil. During this step, the combined seeder brought the seeding material into the soil. After just one year, a change in the species in the meadow was visible, there were many more flowers. Additionally, a change in farmers' perception was noticeable. They no longer mow the entire meadow but leave strips of old grass for insects and birds.

Combination of sustainable land management measures for biodiversity

In the Mostviertel Farmer Cluster, it was observed that farmers are now more aware of the biodiversity on their farms and they know that the combination of different measures brings the most for biodiversity. The Farmer Cluster offered them a pleasant and appreciative space where they could exchange ideas and experiences without interruption. Furthermore, interest in the FRAMEwork project was even aroused among farmers outside the cluster, with the Mostviertel farms serving as multipliers.

- **Speak at eye level and farmer monitoring approach**

An important prerequisite for the establishment of environmentally friendly measures was that farmers could learn from each other. It is very important for farmers to talk to colleagues from the agricultural sector who have sufficient practical knowledge. The Farmer Clusters provided a conducive environment for this. This exchange is excellent for further spreading biodiversity-friendly thinking. Species monitoring by farmers has led to a better understanding of biodiversity and the positive impacts of their implemented measures. This is also essential for sharing knowledge with the public, neighbors and other farmers. They have also learned how many different species they already have around their farms.

- **Graduated meadow use**

Gradual meadow use is an approach that can bring more biodiversity to fields. On the one hand, meadows are extensively cultivated and sown with species-rich seeds. In addition, the meadows are no longer fertilized, which leads to a loss of nutrients. This means that vigorous grasses and herbs are reduced. This allows weaker plants to thrive. The saved fertilizer can be applied to the more intensively cultivated meadows, thus improving yield and efficiency. The Mostviertel cluster initiated this approach by sowing the species-rich smooth oat meadows. The farmers have these meadows and replanted them. In addition, farmers are adapting their mowing regime to the insects' breeding seasons. Very late mowing of the extensive meadows can protect ground-nesting birds and butterfly caterpillars

- **Combination of measures as the key to success**

In the Mostviertel cluster, in addition to seeding the extensive meadows, other measures such as installing nesting boxes and planting windbreak hedges were implemented. Furthermore, flowering strips were established, and strips of mature grass were not mown. This combination can promote insects by providing nesting sites and improved food availability. As a result, birds are also attracted to the area, as the insects also improve their food supply and create additional nesting sites in the hedges. This combination of late cutting and the provision of nesting and feeding sites contributes significantly to the promotion of biodiversity.

Policy implications

Farmers make an important contribution to the preservation of Austria's cultural landscape, as well as to the numerous ecosystem services that nature provides for us humans. The promotion of environmentally friendly measures should therefore be important to all of us.

- **Promoting practice-oriented training**

Education and awareness-raising are a very important part of making agricultural practices sustainable. Farmers should be able to take important measures based on their own conviction. This includes both training courses and courses but also, the exchange between farmers and the joint implementation of measures, as seen here in the Farmer Cluster.

- **Designing funding measures to be easy to implement**

Farmers need measures they can identify with. It is best if farmers' autonomy is respected and if they can decide for themselves what they want to implement and for what benefit. It would make sense to do this in the productive environment of a farmer cluster so that they can find good solutions together. Clusters saw higher engagement when incentives allowed flexible participation and supported peer-led initiatives. Collective result-based payments enhanced conservation outcomes and built peer accountability. Particularly in high-risk settings, collective

payments improved cooperation by leveraging the potential for collective risk-sharing. Policymakers should design incentive structures that are adaptable, locally relevant, and rooted in shared goals.

- **Access to knowledge, advice, and practical tools**

Farmers need more than goodwill—they need the right information at the right time. Platforms like Recodo.io provide open-access training, biodiversity monitoring protocols, and stakeholder engagement resources that empower both facilitators and farmers. These tools enable the adoption of biodiversity-friendly practices and align local actions with broader conservation goals. Policy should ensure that such platforms are widely accessible, regularly updated, and tailored to local contexts.

- **Pay for ecosystem services**

Farmers' care of the landscape and the ecosystem services they maintain, such as avalanche protection through the management of alpine pastures, should be financially compensated. Maintaining ecosystem services contributes to our well-being, tourism, recreation, food production, and our security.

References / Further Reading

Bohnet, I., Thomas, F., Zagata, L., Hardy, C., Fritschle, M., Engel, S., & Kuhfuss, L. (2025). D6.1 Report on the impact of Cluster approach on Farmer's self-identity and behaviour (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15090426>).

To learn more about the FRAMEwork eleven Farmer Cluster, see <https://recodo.io/page/farmer-clusters/farmer-cluster-finder>.

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